

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Forecasts estimate limited cultured meat production through 2050", Applied Stream

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper "Forecasts estimate limited cultured meat production through 2050" [1], a Rethink Priorities project, also posted on the EA Forum [here](#). This was evaluated as part of our “applied and policy stream”, described [here](#). We also asked evaluators to consider this in connection with our Pivotal Question on the viability of cultured meat (see forum discussion [here](#)), and to provide feedback that would help us consider and operationalize this question (see public work [here](#)). The evaluators were fairly positive about the potential for cultured meat and see some of the choices D&Z made as overly pessimistic, with at least one typo in the information provided to the evaluators leaning towards pessimism. They also point to a range of newer TEAs and results. Manheim also argues that even expensive “luxury” cultured meat provides a path forward. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Key content

Evaluations

1. [David Manheim](#)
2. [Estere Seinkmane](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria. However, for this particular case we de-emphasized the ratings aspect. We asked evaluators to focus on (1) whether the claims made in the paper were valid and up-to-date and (2) things that the authors could have done better, particularly considering ways to better plan and structure future synthesis and forecasting exercises better.

Note: Applied and Policy Stream¹

Overall assessment:²

	Overall assessment (0-100)	90% Credible Interval
David Manheim	85	60 - 91
Estere Seinkmane	70	60 - 80

See “[Metrics](#)” below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators’ ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

Evaluation summaries

David Manheim

The review finds Rethink Priorities' 2022 cultured meat forecast methodologically sound but limited and misleading. It critiques the pessimistic framing, exclusion of luxury-product adoption, and potential premature impact on funding. Despite uncertainty on mass scale by 2050, falling input costs and emerging luxury markets suggest greater promise than implied. Still, success depends on scaling, adoption, and investment.

Estere Seinkmane

My evaluation focused on assessing the assumptions and providing up-to-date context and background for the forecasting paper. The paper (post) was published in 2022, and relied on 2020-2021 data. Since then, at least eight cultivated meat (CM) products have been approved, claimed costs are below \$20/kg, CM researchers exceed 250, and total funding surpassed \$3B, coming from VC, public research funding, and philanthropic organisations. The CM definition (cell types, species, % in hybrid products), the media cost components, and other relevant technologies could be clarified, esp. in the context of more novel findings, to improve further CM forecasts.

Metrics

Ratings

	Evaluator 1 David Manheim		Evaluator 2 Estere Seinkmane	
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁴	85	(60, 91)	70	(60, 80)
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵ [Newer form only]	50	(40, 85)		
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁶	92	(80, 94)		

Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁷	84	(80, 94)		
Logic & communication ⁸	50	(43, 67)		
Open, collaborative, replicable ⁹	92	(84, 98)		
Real-world relevance 10 , 11	95	(87, 99)		
Relevance to global priorities ¹² , ¹³	95	(87, 99)		

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ¹⁴	Belief in claim ¹⁵	Suggested robustness checks ¹⁶
Evaluator 1 David Manheim	There is limited promise for scaling to reduce costs of cultured meat enough to greatly reduce consumption of traditional animal farming by 2050.	50-70%	N/A
Evaluator 2 Estere Seinkmane	D&Z state, "The aggregated probabilities from our panel include a 54% probability that less than 100,000 metric tons of cultured meat (where >51% of the 'meat' is produced directly from animal cells) will be produced and sold at any price in a 12-month period before the end of 2051"	Broadly this seems in the right ballpark, though I think the production would be approaching and would already reach 100k ton level in the next 10-20 years with a slightly higher probability (>50%, <70% - though again very hard to say as forecasting here was not my focus)	Specifically on the production volume, I would consult this post from Elliot Schwartz (GFI) estimating current production at 500 metric tons and underlying sources.

References

1. Dullaghan, Neil. 2022. "Forecasts Estimate Limited Cultured Meat Production through 2050." *Rethink Priorities*, March 22, 2022. <https://rethinkpriorities.org/research-area/forecasts-estimate-limited-cultured-meat-production-through-2050/>.

Evaluation manager's discussion

Why we prioritized this research

Our impression: this work, along with the [author's previous post](#) (a comparison of TEAs) may have been somewhat influential in reducing support and funding for the development of cultured meat, particularly in the effective altruism community. E.g., Faunalytics [did a research summary](#) on this. David Humbird's 2020 [techno-economic analysis](#) (TEA), which this work cites heavily, seems have been even more influential. While this work is now somewhat old, it did not seem to have been superseded by a different ~narrative on the EA forum. It also outlined key cruxes, models, and research in a way that was particularly helpful for framing our cultured meat Pivotal Question.

Evaluation process

Overview, guidelines, steps

We asked these evaluators to consider

- the relevance and currency of that work,
- the (updated) implications for the potential for cultured meat (informing our PQ) and
- the approaches D&Z took, and how future work should follow their example or make different choices

The evaluators are fairly positive about the potential for cultured meat and see some of the choices D&Z made as overly pessimistic, with at least one ~typo in the information provided to the evaluators leaning towards pessimism. They also point to a range of newer TEAs and results. And Manheim makes a case that even expensive "luxury" CM provide a path forward.

Following this, we'll ask different sets of evaluators to consider the body of TEAs and related recent research, and to provide structured evaluations of a small set of these, as well as stating their beliefs about a set of operationalized PQs sub-questions. And this will feed into our [Metaculus forecasting community](#) and our overall synthesis.

See [here](#) for our database of PQs, operationalization work, and PQ research being prioritized.

Choice of evaluators

We chose evaluators to balance forecasting, economics, and quantification expertise (Manheim) with expertise in biology and this specific technological context (Seinkmane), as well as some links outside the Effective Altruism/effective animal welfare ecosystem. Neither reported a conflict of interest, nor an inherent stake in promoting cultivated meat (see Seinkmane's disclaimer in the appendix to her report). Both evaluators also provided us feedback on this pivotal questions project and the question operationalization.

COI issues

David Reinstein acted as the co-evaluation manager for this paper, (along with Ashley Meader). Reinstein suggested this paper particularly to inform our Pivotal Question on the viability of cultured meat (see forum discussion [here](#)). David Reinstein worked at Rethink Priorities alongside the authors (although in a different team) from 2021-2023. The first evaluator, David Manheim, is also a Field Specialist at The Unjournal, and voted in favor of prioritizing this research (as did David Reinstein and four other team members).

Author engagement

The authors were aware of this evaluation and shared some helpful thoughts early in the process. They also clarified some details in response to David Manheim (the first evaluator) about a mistake in the information provided to their forecasters. We gave them the opportunity to respond to this, and also reached out to William McAuliffe, a Senior Research Manager at Rethink Priorities. They each declined to respond. (As always, if they respond in future, we will integrate it here.)

Footnotes

1. This paper was evaluated as part of our "applied and policy stream", described [here](#). The ratings should not be directly compared to those in our main academic stream. [↵](#)
2. We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to applied and policy research you have read aiming at a similar audience, and with similar goals." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to future impactful applied research, and practical relevance and usefulness." [↵](#)
3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
4. Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to future impactful applied research, and practical relevance and usefulness. [↵](#)
5. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their

evidence?"

This was on the newer form only [↔](#)

6.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↔](#)

7. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↔](#)

8. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↔](#)

9.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↔](#)

10.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↔](#)

11.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↔](#)

12. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

13.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

14.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↵](#)

15. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you **believe** the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↵](#)

16.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. [↵](#)

References

1. Dullaghan, Neil. 2022. "Forecasts Estimate Limited Cultured Meat Production through 2050." *Rethink Priorities*, March 22, 2022. <https://rethinkpriorities.org/research-area/forecasts-estimate-limited-cultured-meat-production-through-2050/>. ↵